

SEROPREVALENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF TRANSFUSION-TRANSMITTED INFECTIONS AMONG BLOOD DONORS IN SOUTH PUNJAB, PAKISTAN: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17521258>

Keywords

Blood bank, Blood safety, Incidence Prevalence, HBV, HCV, HIV

Article History

Received: 13 September 2025

Accepted: 23 October 2025

Published: 04 November 2025

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Abstract

Background

Transfusion-transmitted infections pose a major threat to the safety of patients receiving blood transfusions, creating significant challenges in maintaining a supply of safe and affordable blood products, particularly in resource-limited healthcare settings. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections among blood donors and to analyze the demographic characteristics of both reactive and non-reactive donors.

Method

A cross-sectional study was conducted at the National Orthopedic and General Hospital, Bahawalpur, from January to December 2023. A total of 300 healthy voluntary blood donors were screened for HBsAg, anti-HCV, HIV, syphilis, and malaria using Immunochromatographic Test (ICT) kits method.

Result

Among the 300 blood donors screened, 30 (10%) were reactive for transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs), with overall prevalence rates of 5.0% for anti-HCV, 3.3% for HBsAg, and 1.7% for syphilis, while no HIV or malaria cases were detected. Statistically significant associations were observed between HBsAg reactivity and gender ($p = 0.006$), age group 19–30 years ($p = 0.022$), and blood group B⁺ ($p = 0.035$). Similarly, anti-HCV positivity showed significant correlations with gender ($p = 0.003$) and education level ($p = 0.012$), indicating higher infection rates among males and literate donors. Syphilis was detected in a small proportion of donors, no significant associations were found with demographic variables ($p > 0.05$). Overall, TTIs were more prevalent among

young (19–30 years), male, literate, and first-time donors, particularly those with B⁺ and O⁺ blood groups.

Conclusion:

This study demonstrated the sero-prevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs) among blood donors, with the highest prevalence observed for HCV, followed by HBV, syphilis, HIV, and malaria. These findings highlight the need for stringent donor selection, promotion of voluntary blood donations, and comprehensive screening of donor blood for TTIs using standardized methods to ensure the safety of blood recipients.

INTRODUCTION

Blood transfusion is crucial to healthcare services globally. The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that approximately 118.2 million blood donations are collected annually worldwide, with a notable 58% of these donations coming from low- and middle-income countries, underscoring the critical role of blood donation in these areas.[1] Blood transfusion is a vital element of healthcare. Blood transfusions rescue millions of lives globally.

In the absence of an artificial alternative, blood remains a critical element in medical and surgical care[2]. During their lifetime, one in three individuals will require blood transfusions and related products. While blood transfusions are crucial for saving millions of lives, unsafe transfusion practices pose a significant risk of transmitting transfusion-transmissible infections (TTIs) to millions of people. [3, 4] To ensure a safe blood supply, practices such as donor deferral, new donor screening assays, and pathogen inactivation of blood components are being implemented. [5, 6] Hepatitis B is among the most prevalent infectious diseases globally. Approximately 2 billion people living today have contracted the hepatitis B virus (HBV) at some stage in their existence.[7] HBV is highly contagious and can easily spread from person to person through blood transfusions, childbirth, unprotected sexual contact, and the sharing of needles. It also has a comparatively higher prevalence in tropical regions.[8] The hepatitis C virus poses a significant health concern globally, with a particularly acute impact in developing countries such as Pakistan. [9] Hepatitis C virus infection can lead to severe outcomes for affected individuals, including chronic liver disease, liver failure, and the development of hepatocellular carcinoma. [10]. The frequency of HCV in a population can be gauged based on factors correlated

with the dissemination of the infection. These factors comprise injecting substance use, infection through contaminated blood products, professional exposure, sexual transmission, and perinatal transmission [11]. In the United States, around 2.7 million people are chronically infected with HCV, with the majority of these cases found among individuals who use illicit drugs or engage in high-risk sexual activities. [12]. Recent research has shown a rise in the incidence of other infections associated with blood transfusions, beyond just HBV and HCV. Notably, this includes Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) caused by HIV, syphilis caused by the bacterium *Treponema pallidum*, and malaria.[13] HIV is a type of human retrovirus that targets and destroys helper (CD4) T lymphocytes, resulting in a weakened immune system and a greatly increased susceptibility to opportunistic infections. [14]. Malaria is most frequently caused by *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Plasmodium malariae*. In the recipient's circulatory system, it can result in the emergence of severe and life-threatening consequences, which can be fatal, particularly in individuals with no previous exposure to malaria or in immunocompromised patients. [15] *Treponema pallidum* is the bacterium responsible for syphilis. It is transmitted through intimate contact with lesions containing the spirochete on the skin or mucous membranes (such as those in the genital area, mouth, or rectum) of an infected individual. Additionally, it can be transmitted from an infected pregnant woman to her fetus.[16]. Transfusion-transmitted syphilis (TTS) is also a major global health concern in low-resource nations. The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that over 90% of the 12 million new syphilis cases diagnosed annually occur in developing countries.[17]

The World Health Organization (WHO) suggests that all donated blood be examined for syphilis and malaria; nevertheless, this presents a substantial obstacle for many under-resourced countries. Blood banks in financially strapped nations often neglect to screen donated blood for syphilis owing to the prohibitive cost for many people.[18]. In Pakistan, around nine million people are affected by Hepatitis B Virus (HBV), ten million by Hepatitis C Virus (HCV), and between 97,000 and 125,000 individuals are living with Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV).[19]

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This cross-sectional study was conducted among blood donors attending the National Orthopedic and General Hospital, Bahawalpur, Pakistan, from January 2023 to December 2023. The study aimed to determine the prevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs) and their association with socio-demographic variables among apparently healthy blood donors.

Sample Collection

A total of 300 blood samples were collected from donors who visited the National Orthopedic and General Hospital, Bahawalpur, during the study period. Each donor was assigned a unique identification number, and relevant information such as name, age, sex, date of birth, occupation, marital status, and contact details was recorded.

Donor Risk Assessment and Data Collection

A structured questionnaire was developed to collect socio-demographic data and potential risk factors. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to inclusion. Before donation, each potential donor completed a detailed health history questionnaire and underwent a brief confidential interview with a trained medical officer. The questionnaire included information regarding general health, lifestyle habits, current or past febrile illnesses, history of weight loss or chronic disease, unusual or excessive bleeding, drug and medication history, tattooing, body piercing, dental treatment, previous blood donation or transfusion, history of travel or immigration, sexual history, and other risk behaviors.

Clinical Screening and Donor Selection

All potential donors underwent baseline screening including a complete blood count (CBC) to exclude individuals with anemia (hemoglobin < 12.5 g/dL), infections, or thrombocytopenia. A physical examination was performed to identify any signs of drug abuse, jaundice, or skin lesions at venipuncture sites. Donors with any contraindication were deferred from donation. Strict aseptic precautions were observed during blood collection, and blood units were properly labeled and stored under standard conditions.

Inclusion Criteria

Donors were included if they were aged between 15 and 55 years, physically healthy and fit for donation, weighed at least 50 kilograms, had a hemoglobin level of 12.5 g/dL or higher, and provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Potential donors were excluded if they were below 15 years of age or weighed less than 50 kilograms, were anemic or appeared malnourished, had a history of jaundice, malaria, or asthma, reported unsafe sexual practices, drug abuse, or other high-risk behaviors, had a previous history of HBV, HCV, HIV, or syphilis, or were clinically unfit or unhealthy at the time of donation.

Laboratory Testing

Venous blood samples were collected using sterile vacutainers. Serum was separated by centrifugation and stored appropriately until testing. Screening for Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg), anti-Hepatitis C virus antibodies (anti-HCV), Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Syphilis, and Malaria was performed using the Immuno-Chromatographic Test (ICT) method (Abbott Diagnostics, USA). All tests were conducted according to the manufacturer's instructions, and reactive samples were re-tested for confirmation.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic

characteristics and infection prevalence. The Chi-square test was applied to determine associations between infection status and socio-demographic variables. Logistic regression analysis was performed to calculate odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) to assess predictors of infection. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Result

During one year duration of study, total 300 patients came to hospital for blood donation and they were screened for TTIs. Three hundred donors were included in study. The results are shown wise in (table-1). Table 1 summarizes the demographic profile of the study participants (N = 300). The findings reveal that the majority of blood donors were male (91.7%), with females representing a smaller proportion (8.3%). The study participants had a mean age of 28.6 ± 2 years (range: 18–55 years). Most donors belonged to the 19–30 years age group (52.0%), followed by those aged 31–40 years (22.7%), while smaller proportions were observed among participants aged ≤ 18 years

(14.7%), 41–50 years (7.7%), and above 50 years (3.0%), indicating that blood donation was predominantly practiced by young adults. The distribution of blood groups showed that B Positive (35.3%) was the most common, followed by O Positive (32.0%) and A Positive (22.3%), whereas negative blood groups were relatively rare.

In case of occupation, students constituted the largest group (38.0%), followed by individuals employed in private or government sectors (32.3%), construction workers/laborers (16.7%), drivers (7.0%), and businessmen (6.0%). Regarding education, a majority of the participants were literate (75.3%), while 24.7% were illiterate. Most donors (71.3%) were first-time participants, whereas 28.7% had donated blood previously. With respect to marital status, more than half of the respondents were married (59.7%), followed by unmarried (37.7%) and divorced individuals (2.7%). Furthermore, a greater proportion of participants resided in urban areas (60.0%) compared to rural regions (40.0%).

Table 1 Descriptive of Socio-demographic Variables among Blood Donors

Demographic variables		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender			
	Male	275	91.7
	Female	8.3	25
	Total	300	100
Age (years)			
	≤ 18	44	14.7
	19–30	156	52.0
	31–40	68	22.7
	41–50	23	7.7
	>50	9	3.0
	Total	300	100
Blood Group			
	A Positive	67	22.3
	B Positive	106	35.3
	AB Positive	12	4.0
	O Positive	96	32.0
	A Negative	2	0.7

	B Negative	6	2.0
	AB Negative	3	1.0
	O Negative	8	2.7
	Total	300	100
Occupation			
	Student	114	38.0
	Businessman	18	6.0
	Driver	21	7.0
	Employee (Private/Govt.)	97	32.3
	Construction Worker/Laborer	50	16.7
	Total	300	100
Education			
	Illiterate	74	24.7
	Literate (Primary- Above)	226	75.3
	Total	300	100
Number of Donations			
	First Donation	214	71.3
	Repeat Donation	86	28.7
	Total	300	100
Marital Status			
	Unmarried	113	37.7
	Married	179	59.7
	Divorced	8	2.7
	Total	300	100
Resident			
	Rural	120	40.0
	Urban	180	60.0
	Total	300	100

The prevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs) among blood donors (n = 300) showed that the highest proportion was observed for Anti-HCV (5.0%), followed by HBsAg (3.3%) and Syphilis (1.7%). No cases of HIV or malaria infection were detected among the study participants, indicating

that hepatitis C virus infection was the most common transfusion-transmitted infection in this donor population (Figure 1).

Fig 1. Prevalence of Transfusion Transmitted Infections (TTIs) among Blood Donors
 Prevalence of Transfusion Transmitted Infection among Blood Donors (n=300)

The demographic characteristics of reactive and non-reactive blood donors (N = 300) is presented in Table 2. Among the total donors, 30 (10%) were reactive for transfusion-transmitted infections, while 270 (90%) were non-reactive. The majority of reactive donors were male (76.7%) and predominantly belonged to the 19–30 years age group (60%), suggesting a higher prevalence of infection among young adults. Reactivity was most frequently observed among individuals with O Positive (40%) and A Positive

(30%) blood groups. In terms of occupation, students (40%) and employees in private or government sectors (26.7%) showed higher proportions of reactivity. A greater proportion of reactive cases were found among literate donors (63.3%) and first-time donors (73.3%). Most reactive donors were unmarried (63.3%), and the distribution of reactivity was equal between urban (50%) and rural (50%) populations.

Table 2 Demographic variables of reactive and non-reactive blood donors

Demographic variables	Total	Non-Reactive	Reactive
Gender			
Male	275	252	23
Female	25	18	7
Total	300	270	30
Age (years)			
≤18	44	41	3
19–30	156	138	18
31–40	68	61	7
41–50	23	22	1
>50	9	8	1
Total	300	270	30
Blood Group			
A Positive	67	58	9

	B Positive	106	99	7
	AB Positive	12	12	0
	O Positive	96	84	12
	A Negative	2	2	0
	B Negative	6	4	2
	AB Negative	3	3	0
	O Negative	8	8	0
	Total	300	270	30
Occupation				
	Student	114	102	12
	Businessman	18	17	1
	Driver	21	18	3
	Employee (Private/Govt.)	97	89	8
	Construction Worker/Laborer	50	44	6
	Total	300	274	26
Education				
	Illiterate	74	63	11
	Literate (Primary- Above)	226	207	19
	Total	300	270	30
Number of Donations				
	First Donation	214	192	22
	Repeat Donation	86	78	8
	Total	300	270	30
Marital Status				
	Unmarried	113	94	19
	Married	179	170	9
	Divorced	8	6	2
	Total	300	270	30
Resident				
	Rural	120	105	15
	Urban	180	165	15
	Total	300	270	30

The distribution of transfusion-transmitted infections (HBsAg, anti-HCV, and syphilis) among reactive and non-reactive blood donors across different demographic variables is presented in Table 3. Among 300 donors, 10 (3.3%) were HBsAg reactive, 15 (5.0%) Anti-HCV reactive, and 5 (1.7%) Syphilis reactive. A significantly higher prevalence of HBsAg ($p = 0.006$) and Anti-HCV ($p = 0.003$) was noted among females. Donors aged 19–30 years showed the highest reactivity, indicating increased susceptibility in younger adults. O Positive and A

Positive blood groups showed higher infection rates, with a significant association between B Positive and HBsAg ($p = 0.035$). Anti-HCV infection showed a significant link with literacy ($p = 0.012$). Most infections occurred among first-time and unmarried donors, while no significant difference was observed by residence or occupation. Overall, Anti-HCV was the most prevalent infection among the study population.

Table 3 Demographic variables of Transfusion Transmitted Infections among reactive and non-reactive blood donors

Demographic variables	HbsAg (n=10)			Anti HCV (n=15)			Syphilis (n=5)		
	Non- Reacti ve	Reacti ve	P value	Non- Reacti ve	Re act ive	P value	Non- Reactiv e	Reacti ve	P value
Gender									
Male	267	8	0.006	265	10	0.003	270	5	0.986
Female*	23	2		20	5		25	0	
Age (years)									
≤18	44	0	0.994	43	1	0.998	42	2	0.997
19-30	149	7	0.022	148	8	0.998	153	3	0.998
31-40	67	1	0.007	62	6	0.998	68	0	1.000
41-50	22	1	0.067	23	0	1.000	23	0	1.000
>50*	8	1		9	0		9	0	
Blood Group									
A Negative	2	0		2	0		2	0	
B Negative	6	0	0.998	5	1	0.059	5	1	0.983
AB Negative	3	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0.999
O Negative	8	0	0.997	8	0	0.997	8	0	1.000
A Positive	64	3	0.552	63	4	0.268	65	2	0.208
B Positive	105	1	0.035	101	5	0.719	105	1	.672
AB Positive	12	0	0.996	12	0	0.996	12	0	0.997
O Positive*	90	6		91	5		95	1	
Occupation									
Student	111	3	0.949	108	6	0.169	111	3	0.995
Businessman	18	0	0.998	17	1	0.635	18	0	1.000
Driver	21	0	0.996	19	2	0.336	20	1	0.994
Employee (Private/Govt.)	92	5	0.975	94	3	0.135	97	0	0.993
Construction Worker/Laborer*	48	2		47	3		49	1	
Education									
Illiterate	70	4	0.147	67	7	0.012	74	0	0.990
Literate (Primary-Above)*	220	6		218	8		221	5	
Number of Donations									
First Donation	208	6	0.489	202	12	0.794	210	4	0.994
Repeat Donation*	82	4		83	3		85	1	
Marital Status									
Unmarried*	175	4		168	11		175	4	
Married	108	5	0.824	19	4	0.367	113	0	0.993
Divorced	7	1	0.287	8	0	0.997	7	1	0.994
Resident									

Rural	17	3	0.071	111	9	0.432	117	3	0.251
Urban*	173	7		174	6		178	2	

*reference Category □ $p < 0.05$ → significant difference □ $p \geq 0.05$ → not significant The figure 2 showed that the comparison HBV and HCV reactivity among blood donors across various demographic variables. Among 289 donors, HBV reactivity was observed in 7 cases (2.4%) and HCV in 9 cases (3.1%), with both infections more prevalent among males. The highest reactivity for both infections occurred in the 19–30 years age group, indicating increased susceptibility among young adults. O Positive and B Positive blood groups showed the highest frequencies of infection. Most reactive cases were found among literate, first-time, and unmarried donors, with slightly higher HCV prevalence in urban residents.

Figure 2. Comparison of HBV and HCV Reactivity According to Demographic Characteristics of Blood Donors

The figure 3 illustrates the significant associations ($p < 0.05$) between transfusion-transmitted infections (HBsAg, Anti-HCV, and Syphilis) and various demographic variables among blood donors. A statistically significant association was observed between HBsAg reactivity and gender, age, blood group, and occupation, while Anti-HCV showed significant correlations with gender, age, and

education. In contrast, Syphilis demonstrated no significant association with any demographic variable. These findings indicate that hepatitis infections (HBV and HCV) are more influenced by demographic factors compared to Syphilis among the study population.

Figure 3. Significant Associations ($P < 0.05$) among Demographic Variables and Infections

Discussion

Blood transfusion is a vital procedure in modern medicine. Rigorous blood screening not only provides insight into the prevalence of transfusion-transmissible infections (TTIs) among healthy individuals but also ensures the safe provision of blood and its components [20]. Reliable disease burden assessments based on sound epidemiological studies serve as a foundation for public health policies. Likewise, accurate evaluation of TTI risks is essential for monitoring blood safety and assessing the effectiveness of current screening methods, as highlighted by Busch et al. [21]. A study conducted in Pakistan revealed that most blood donors are first-time donors, which may reflect the actual infection rate within the community [20]. However, other research suggests that blood donors may not accurately represent the general population, as prevalence rates could be either underestimated or

overestimated due to their distinct demographic characteristics [22, 23].

Since the majority of donors are young or middle-aged males, this population group may not accurately capture the true prevalence, particularly as females constitute more than half of Pakistan's population. Therefore, this viewpoint appears more credible than the previous one. Nonetheless, the prevalence of TTIs among blood donors in a well-organized healthcare system, supported by an efficient blood service network, can serve as a dependable indicator for estimating the presence of infectious agents transmissible through blood products in the wider population, as discussed by Gharehbaghian and Chandra et al. [24, 25].

This study investigated the prevalence and demographic correlates of **transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs)** among blood donors in a tertiary

care setting in Pakistan. A total of 300 blood donors were screened for major TTIs, including Hepatitis B virus (HBV), Hepatitis C virus (HCV), Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), syphilis, and malaria. The overall TTI reactivity was 10%, with HCV being the most prevalent infection (5.0%), followed by HBsAg (3.3%) and syphilis (1.7%). None of the donors tested positive for HIV or malaria. These findings highlight both progress and persistent challenges in ensuring blood safety in Pakistan and other developing countries.

The **overall TTI prevalence (10%)** observed in this study is broadly consistent with national estimates from various regions of **Pakistan**, where prevalence rates among blood donors range from 8% to 12% [26]. Similar prevalence levels have been reported in **India (6–10%)** [27, 28] and **Nepal (9%)** [29], reflecting shared regional risk factors such as limited public health infrastructure, inadequate infection control practices, and variations in vaccination coverage. In contrast, **developed nations** such as the **United States** and **United Kingdom** report significantly lower donor infection rates—typically below 1%—due to more stringent donor selection criteria, universal screening with nucleic acid testing (NAT), and widespread hepatitis B vaccination [30, 31].

In **Pakistan**, TTIs remain a major public health issue, particularly HCV, which the **World Health Organization (WHO)** classifies as a **high-burden infection**, with a national community prevalence estimated at **4.9%**[32]. Similar challenges exist in other low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where untested transfusions, unsafe medical injections, and limited awareness perpetuate transmission [33]. Therefore, our findings reinforce the continuing need for improved donor education and strengthened screening programs.

HCV infection was the **most frequent TTI** in this study (5.0%), consistent with findings from **Punjab and Sindh provinces of Pakistan**, where reported HCV prevalence among donors ranges between **4% and 6%** [26] [34]. The predominance of HCV over HBV reflects persistent community transmission and potential iatrogenic exposure through unsafe medical or dental procedures [35] [36]. Comparatively, the prevalence of HCV among blood donors is lower in **India (0.5–1.5%)** [27, 28], **Bangladesh (0.95%)**[37], and **Iran (0.8–2.5%)** [38], highlighting Pakistan's

disproportionately high burden. A notable finding was the significant association between **HCV reactivity and gender, age, and education level**. Males, particularly those aged 19–30 years, were more likely to be reactive. These results align with previous research from **Nepal** and **Iran**, where young male donors exhibited the highest HCV rates [29, 38]. This pattern may be linked to behavioral factors such as unsafe barber practices, needle reuse, or increased healthcare exposure. Interestingly, a higher proportion of **literate donors** were reactive for Anti-HCV. This may be explained by greater healthcare utilization and thus higher potential exposure to medical procedures rather than a lack of awareness.

HBsAg positivity was 3.3% in this study, which lies within the **intermediate endemicity range (2–7%)** reported by the **WHO** for Pakistan [26, 32] [36]. This finding aligns closely with data from **India (1.0–3.5%)** [27], **Bangladesh (0.95%)** [37], and **Iran (2.5%)** [38]. The relatively lower prevalence compared with older Pakistani studies suggests some success of the **National Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI)**, which introduced HBV vaccination for infants in 2002 [31]. However, adults born before this initiative remain unvaccinated, perpetuating HBV transmission among young male populations. Significant associations were found between **HBsAg reactivity and gender, age, blood group, and occupation**. Similar trends have been reported by Raza et al. [34] and Zorob et al. [36], indicating that behavioral risk factors and occupational exposure contribute to infection risk. Male donors, especially those in occupations involving physical labor or frequent contact with others (e.g., barbers, healthcare workers), are more likely to encounter infected blood or instruments. These findings emphasize the need for targeted vaccination campaigns and awareness drives among high-risk occupational groups.

The prevalence of **syphilis (1.7%)** among donors was low, comparable to studies from **India (1.2%)**[27] and high from **Bangladesh (0.95%)** [37], and **Nigeria (1.0%)** [28]. A similar low rate (1.3%) was reported in **Turkey** [39]. The absence of statistically significant associations between syphilis reactivity and demographic characteristics suggests that sexual health awareness and safe behavior practices may have improved in recent years. However, the continued detection of reactive samples underscores the

importance of maintaining syphilis screening as part of the routine pre-donation testing panel. Even a small number of missed infections can lead to serious transfusion-related complications.

Most donors in this study were **male (91.7%)**, with a majority aged **19–30 years**, which reflects patterns observed across South Asia [26, 27] [34]. Male predominance in blood donation is often attributed to physiological constraints (menstruation, anemia risk) and sociocultural factors limiting female participation [27, 28]. The higher TTI reactivity among males (76.7% of total reactive donors) supports global data indicating that men have higher exposure to risk behaviors and healthcare procedures [28][40]. Moreover, **first-time donors (73.3%)** exhibited higher reactivity rates compared to repeat donors, consistent with national [34] and international findings [38] [39]. Repeat donors tend to be safer due to previous screening and self-deferral of high-risk individuals. Encouraging **voluntary, repeat donations** is thus a crucial public health strategy for reducing TTI risk. Interestingly, infection rates were comparable between **urban (50%)** and **rural (50%)** donors, indicating that both populations face similar exposure risks [35]. This finding suggests that infection control challenges are widespread and not limited to specific geographic regions within Pakistan.

Limitations

This study was conducted at a single center with a modest sample size, which may limit generalizability. Additionally, behavioral risk factors such as injection drug use, sexual behavior, and past transfusion history were not evaluated. The absence of **nucleic acid testing (NAT)** could have resulted in underestimation of early-stage infections. Nevertheless, the findings offer valuable insights into current TTI trends among donors and can inform local and national policy interventions.

Conclusion

This study find that a significant proportion of blood donors carried transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs), with HCV and HBV remaining the most prevalent in Pakistan. The higher infection rates among young male first-time donors emphasize the need for stricter donor selection, voluntary donations,

and comprehensive screening for HCV, HBV, HIV, syphilis, and malaria... Future research assessing donors' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors can further enhance blood safety. Overall, continuous education, vaccination, and molecular testing will improve public health and would increase blood safety and quality

Declaration

Abbreviations

CBC: Complete blood count; HBV: Hepatitis B virus; HCV: Hepatitis C virus; HIV: human immunodeficiency virus; ICT: Immunochromatographic test; TTIs: Transfusion-transmitted infections; WHO: World Health Organization

Acknowledgements

The authors would also like to acknowledge the donor's area for their support in conducting interviews and the ethics committee for their approval to conduct this study

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Written informed consent was taken from all donors. This study was approved by the hospital ethics committee (NOGHB Ethics Committee).

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

This research was not funded by any university, organization, or external agency.

Availability of data and materials

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are not publicly available due to hospital ethical policy in order to protect participant confidentiality

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Authors' contributions

M.A.M. conceived and designed the study. M.A.M. and E.E. developed the study protocol, collected and analyzed the data, interpreted the results, and drafted the manuscript. M.A.M. supervised the study and critically reviewed the manuscript. K.I. and S.S. contributed to clinical interpretation and participant recruitment. W.K. and U.H. conducted literature review and supported data entry. E.E. and R.A. performed laboratory investigations and contributed to statistical analysis. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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